

ADDRESSING THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE PERFORMANCE OF UNDERGRADUATE FEMALE STUDENTS IN ENGLISH COMMUNICATION

By

Haliru Ibrahim Gidadawa

Department of English Language and Linguistics,
Sokoto State University, Sokoto

Abstract

This paper attempts to explore the various factors affecting the performance of undergraduate female students in English communication, giving particular reference to Sokoto State University. Communication in English is the process of sharing with another person or group one's knowledge, interest, attitudes, opinions, feelings, and ideas using the English medium either through the exchange of verbal or written messages. However, in a university setting where students are to focus attention on their core areas of study, skills in the English language are considered as something not necessary and is mainly for students of English. This affects students' overall performance in written and oral communication throughout their stay at the university and even after graduation. And with the compulsory Communication in English course for all new undergraduate students, female students are faced with several factors such as the difficulty of learning modules, the pairing of student groups, stage fright problem, teaching approach, and large class effect among others affecting their performance. How these affect female students and in what ways the factors could be addressed are part of the questions the paper seeks to answer. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) interview was used on a sample of one hundred and fifty (150) undergraduate female students of Sokoto State University across the Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Science and Education. The study discovered that, there is more focus on grammar in the learning modules the other than aspects of communication, and that, the teaching approaches do little to minimize learners' stage fright and large class effect. These lessen the positive impact that communication in English Courses should have on many female learners. The study concluded by suggesting ways of enhancing the performance of female students both in spoken and written aspects as graduates of university to enable them compete with their male counterparts in expressing their abilities and talents in any communicative situation.

Key Words: *Communication, Performance & Female Undergraduates*

Introduction

The term communication can simply be viewed as the symbolic interaction of two or more persons. And if communication is to occur, on one hand, some stimulus must be received¹, and on the other hand, the potential receiver of the message must be intelligible². Thus, communication is the process by which information is shared whether by a person or group through the exchange of verbal and or written messages. Communication in English which is the focus of the paper, is the process of sharing with another person or group, one's knowledge or ideas through the English medium whether to pass information, raise awareness or to educate and enlighten. Okejara (1990)³ pointed out that a great deal of what is written in English is written with the sound of it in the writer's mind. Thus, in our speech, we may want to get something done (imperatives or commands), or to seek factual information (interrogatives/questions), etc. In our writing, we want to express our ideas for potential use either in performing tasks such as recording

messages or presenting our ideas or talents for gainful purposes.

However, in a country such as Nigeria, where English is an added language, a major official language, a lingua franca, and the language of instruction in the educational system, a communicative level of proficiency in it is expected from graduates of higher institutions, especially the universities. This is why there is the need for devoting greater attention to the achievement of improved knowledge of English and the acquisition of adequate oral and written skills in it. This Maybe be part of the reasons for the establishment of General Studies Division in all Nigeria's Tertiary institutions generally to produce well-rounded morally and intellectually capable graduates with vision and entrepreneurial skills in an environment of peace and social cohesiveness. Similarly, part of the objectives of this important division is the production of graduates capable of communicating effectively both orally and in writing⁴.

¹ Stimulus here refers to signals either in spoken or written form, or sometimes in sign form as with the case of the deaf produced by a speaker in a communicative situation.

² The addressee in a communicative situation must have the ability to receive and interpret the signal or message received from the speaker through comprehension processes which include lexical, literal, interpretive, applied and affective comprehension.

³ Okejara (1990) was categorically referring to the connection between the proficiency of a speaker in a language and the ability to understand how to express himself or herself via the language. As such, one's ability to communicate depends largely on the proficiency he or she has of the language they intend to use for such communicative task.

⁴ To achieve this objective, in every tertiary institution in Nigeria, there is a department or

Over the years, female graduates from Nigerian universities are yet to be clearly and positively identified with adequate communicative proficiency in English pronunciation, let alone articulateness in speech, correctness of grammar and usage, or elegance and style in the choice of appropriate communication skills for use in the various administrative and professional job opportunities available in the labour market. We owe this observation to Abdul (2007), Maru (2007) and Mamo (2016) who all believed that low esteem and poor proficiency in the English language evident among female students is truly due to the shortcoming of communication in English courses at the higher institutions particularly the university to train them well and equip them with the right skills to think and talk in the English medium within and outside the school environment.

On a particular note, in the past four years, Sokoto State University has been running communication in English courses I and 2 meant to inculcate the

skills necessary to prepare its students to face the challenges of communication needs within and outside the university environment through the English medium. However, data obtained from the General Studies Division of the University, indicating the performance output of both male and female students in the last two years, reveals that something needs to be done to enable female students to positively benefit from communication in English courses. For example, the population of male and female students as of 2018/2019 and 2019/2020 stands at 63/37% and 66/24% respectively, while the overall best-performing students both in written examinations and oral presentations are male with the least performing students to be the females⁵. To understand how far this has been the case, the paper conducted a survey on female students and obtained relevant data with a view to the understanding the learning situation which could help to achieve maximum success.

division in charge of handling the teaching of courses perceived to have the ingredients for producing graduates well-rounded morally and intellectually with vision and entrepreneurial skills in an environment of peace and social cohesiveness. At the university level, the division is charged with the full responsibility of administering anything that has to do with the administration and teaching processes, with courses spread from 100 to 300 levels.

⁵ Pennacchia, Jones and Aldridge's (2008) submission is part of the answer to this situation. The current study finds many undergraduate students from the faculty of science having little interest and confidence in learning the skills of English communication due to their prior experiences such as the perception they had at secondary schools that English teachers make lots of noise and are not straight to the point. This is proven to be true as many of the science students do well in summary skills.

Pennacchia, Jones and Aldridge (2008) thought that a long break from learning and prior learning experiences sometimes results in a lack of confidence among learners in a communicative setting which will directly or indirectly affect their performances. Owing to this observation, one may find learners, particularly female undergraduates, who either had a long break from the learning of English communication skills or had poor prior experiences in the learning of English as a subject, having little confidence to perform well in the learning of English Communication skill at the university.

Performance Situation of Undergraduate Female Students from Contemporary Studies in Communication in English Classes

Scholars such as Al-Roud (2015), Dhillon (2016), Abdulrahuman (2017) and Agustia (2017) conducted various empirical studies on the aspect of second language learning with English as the target language. However, while Al-Roud (2015) attempted to find out the extent of the effect of English Language in Learning the Arabic Language for Undergraduate Students in Bridge-water

State University, Dhillon (2016) researched on the factors affecting the proficiency of English pronunciation among Batak Toba language speakers. Similarly, while Abdulrahuman (2017) conducted research on mother tongue influence on the learning of English as a second language and related issues among Tamil speaking students, Agustia (2017) researched on the type of Indonesian interference found in the English language among class VIII SMPK 2 Harapan Untal-Untal students. All these scholars showed interest in factors affecting the learning of English as a second language, they seemed to focus attention on mother tongue interference mainly as the contributing factor to problems of learning English as a second language. They also paid little attention to gender peculiarities about language proficiency.

Unlike Al-Roud (2015), Dhillon⁶ (2016), Abdulrahuman (2017), and Agustia (2017), according to newer data based on empirical research by Mulac (1999) and others, rendered more concrete insights into gendered language. Although all features identified and presented here are used by both men and women, there are clear differences in the frequency of usage

⁶ Although the current study is not concerned specifically about gendered language, Mulac (1999) empirical findings largely from the work of Braun, (2004) has opened our eyes to the communicative tendencies of female learners and

gave us clues as some the reasons why communication in English as a course will help female undergraduates fair well against their male undergraduate counterparts.

between the genders (Braun, 2004: 16). Firstly, women tend to use more intensifying adverbs such as “very” or “really” (Braun, 2004: 15). Women’s sentence structures involve the more frequent use of tag questions, questions in general, and hedges (Braun, 2004: 15). Together with a female style of conversation that is more polite and contains indirect orders rather than imperatives (Braun, 2004: 15), this could be categorized as an absence of dominant behavior. Men, on the other hand, use more directives (Braun, 2004: 15). They also behave more competitively in conversations, for example interrupting and talking more often than their female conversational partners (Braun, 2004: 15). By contrast, women display a more cooperative style of conversational interactions including minimal reaction to mark interest with such devices as “yes” or “mhm” (Braun, 2004: 15). In terms of sentence structure, women adhere more closely to the norms of the standard language. Men, on the other hand, are seen

to talk more colloquially and make greater use of dialect. Women talk in sentences of average length, often introducing their sentences with an adverbial clause, and their sentences contain subordinate clauses. Men’s ways of speaking are less grammatical and more elliptic. When it comes to the actual subject matter of the utterances men and women make, women relate what they say to emotions and they speak more personally. Men’s speech is less emotional and more factual, using a greater amount of locatives and terms relating to quantity. They are also more judgmental in their utterances and relate more consistently to themselves⁷.

Wold (2006), in his study on the difficulties in Learning English as a Second or Foreign Language, the author explored the experience of one adult female immigrant to the United States and her difficulties in learning English as a second language (ESL). He identified several compounding reasons for her lack of expected progress. The researcher accomplished the study through personal

⁷ In a more related sense, Shaywitz et al. (1995) found sex differences in the functional brain organization for language in a study that used echo-planar functional magnetic resonance imaging across three different tasks, that is, orthographic, semantic and phonological (rhyme). It was added that, during phonological processing, males exhibited left lateralized brain activity, while in females more widely-distributed neural systems were engaged. The same finding of cerebral laterality emerged in a study which

focused on both language (a timed rhyme-matching task) and visuo-spatial processing (Clements et al., 2006). The evidence pointed to lateralization differences between the two sexes, that is men were more left lateralized when performing the phonological task, but bilateral in the visuo-spatial task, while female brains showed activity in both hemispheres for phonological processing and were more right lateralized for the visuo-spatial task.

observation and interviews, which allowed the learner to tell her own story in the phenomenological case study. Many challenges confront the foreign language (FL) learners and the learner struggled with notable difficulties. The findings showed that the learner, whose first and second languages were non-alphabetical, had never been taught the sound/letter rules system of English, and this fundamental deficit played a pivotal role in her poor classroom attendance, wavering motivation to learn and practice English, and ultimately, in her lack of progress⁸. This study although centred on one individual student has however established interesting facts worthy of consideration by scholars interested in Applied Linguistic studies of second language learners.

Performance Situation of Undergraduate Female Students of Sokoto State University in Communication in English Classes

It is a fact that, at Sokoto State University like any other learning institution, everyone who comes to the university learns and communicates using English rapidly or makes effective progress in English ability whether they are in the arts, sciences, or somewhere else. And that lack of progress can hurt the quality of education of the learner and can be a

barrier to success for the learner after graduation. The resulting social marginalization might be particularly more frustrating for an undergraduate female learner, as she may feel increasingly marginalized from the system of a career she seeks to join or establish. That frustration can compound the effects and causes of the perceived failure to progress. As such, the need to address the problem cannot be overemphasised.

However, data obtained from the university shows some significant improvement in terms of percentage pass of female students who took the communication in English courses within the period of the four sessions reviewed. However, there are indications that a lot need to be done to improve the situation. Consider the output below:

SESSION	PASS %	FAIL %	INCREMENT %
2016/2017	54	45	-
2017/2018	61	39	+7
2018/2019	63	37	+2
2019/2020	71	29	+8

Table 1a: Performance of female undergraduates in communication in English course 1

⁸ Anything thing that affects learner motivation in a learning process will go a long way to have negative consequences on the learning process.

SESSION	PASS %	FAIL %	INCREMENT %
2016/2017	61	39	-
2017/2018	69	31	+8
2018/2019	68	32	-1
2019/2020	71	29	+3

Table 1b: Performance of female undergraduates in communication in English course 2

It could be observed from the tables above that, although the rate of pass is above the average of 50%, in both courses for all the sessions, the fact that many female students failed in their attempt to pass the courses shows there is still need for something to be done to improve the situation particularly with regards what the female undergraduate perceived to be the cause of the problem.

Methodology

The study employed the Descriptive Survey Method proposed by Cooper & Schindler (2003) in the collection of its data from which results were yielded. The data involves both primary data, comprising responses from Focus Group Discussion (FGD) interviews, and secondary data consisting of scholarly materials like course syllabus, lecture notes and end of semester results. The purpose of descriptive research is to state the condition of events as they exist at present to provide possible solutions. The area of the study is the communication domain within which the study focuses

mainly on English communication which has been a compulsory course for all undergraduate students of Nigerian universities.

About the Participants

The undergraduate female students of Sokoto State University are grouped into two by the study. The first group is termed 'sessional', while the second is 'post-sessional'. The 'Sessional' group comprises female undergraduates who are in 100 level going through the learning process of the Communication in English course. Sixty (60) students were involved in the study from this group across the three faculties.

The 'Post-Sessional' group comprises female undergraduates who are in 200 to 400 levels, and have completed the learning process of the Communication in English courses. Ninety (90) students were involved in the study from this group across the three faculties. The two groups participated in the study FGD.

Findings of the Study

From the resultant output of the respondents engaged in the FGD, the study was able to find out the following upon which conclusion was drawn in addition to suggestions for policy and practical solutions:

Communication in English Courses 1 and 2 at Sokoto State University

are both offered at 100 level (first and second semesters respectively) as contained in the latest NUC Bench Mark (2018). This means all Direct Entry students (who join at 200 level) are not opportune to learn any of them. This makes the learning of the two courses among 100 level students (particularly those from science-oriented departments) too much on the one hand, and on the other hand, it means absence of learning opportunity of the courses for Direct Entry students – a deficit which may affect their communicative performances in their academic career.

Secondly, classes for communication in English courses at the university are arranged with an average number of 300 students per class – a number exceedingly regarded as a large class as Sanchez (2015) defines it, and which comes with a number of learning challenges and problems, one of which is limiting interaction. And interaction is critical to the process of learning a second language. According to Ellis (1999, as cited in Moss & Ross-Feldman, 2003), interaction contributes to second language acquisition when individuals communicate, especially when they negotiate meaning in order to prevent communication breakdown.

Thirdly, female undergraduates at the university are reduced to subordinate learners in the sense that, male students

most at times hijack group works and class presentations. And that was because instructors do not usually assign specific roles to group members but allow the group to decide. This demotivates them the female in the learning process. And learning a second language is clearly a challenge that requires much motivation, particularly for female learners. And, as Comstock & Kamara, (2003) and Schwarz, (2003) put it, failure, weaknesses, and difficulties in learning the new language arrive mostly due to lack of motivation and can have negative effects on academic pursuits, social interactions and personal relationships as well as learner self-esteem. In addition, Moss and Ross-Feldman (2003) was of the opinion that, group dynamics, and even a partner's motivation, affect a learner's attitude, effort, classroom behaviour and successful language acquisition.

Fourthly, many of the respondents believe they are being taught English grammar rather than communication skills. Most science-based students believe this might be the reason why most of the aspects taught to them are difficult. Some respondents from the science faculty wondered why they need to learn figures of speech like simile, metaphors among others when in reality they use straight forward science-language in their communication. And looking at the content of the course syllabus, one will

agree to some extent that, the respondents' claim is slightly true. Very little aspect about communication is included in the syllabus. Besides, the idea behind the modelling of the course from 'Use of English' to 'Communication in English' in the updated bench mark is to move away from the teaching of core grammar to a more communicative language teaching. And despite this change, the syllabus remains almost the same.

Additionally, the large nature of the communication in English classes makes it difficult to apply any checking measure to properly ensure students attendance. Besides, sometimes students will be standing or hanging around door entrances during classes. So, no matter how instructors wish to take attendances, they will always be corrupted with absentees by students. And making roll calls will take nearly an hour out of the two hours meant for the class. This scenario sometimes makes female students unable to withstand the difficulties and resort to shunting the classes. Also, the large class effect has a significant contribution in adding to the problem of stage fright among the female undergraduates. Most of the respondents testified having sometimes experienced fear, nervousness, and anxiety whenever asked to appear before the class to make contributions. This hindered them from participation in interaction that could have

played a key role in their continued learning. Although instructors do encourage them to overcome the fright, the large number of students in the hall majority of who are male, is always a difficult barrier to overcome.

Conclusion

From the foregoing discussion, it is safe to conclude that, female undergraduate students at Sokoto State University do face some challenges with regards to the learning process of communication in English course. The paper reported that, these challenges directly affect them in their quest to benefit from the impact the course was designed to have on them. Although there is another paper that critically tests the female undergraduate group of learners with a view to understanding how difficult it is to learn the aspects in the GST 111 and 112 Classes among other issues, the current paper looked at the general concerns of the affected learners with regards to difficulty of learning modules, the pairing of student groups, stage fright problem, teaching approach, and large class effect among others.

Suggestions for Policy and Practice

There is need to revert to the former model of teaching communication in English courses where one course is taught at 100 level, and the second course at 200 level.

This is to allow Direct Entry students who join the university at 200 level to have the opportunity to learn communication skills during their academic program.

The mode of evaluation or assessment does not help the learning situation. Learners are evaluated only through the written medium. And for communication classes, there should also be proper attention to oral competencies. Learners should be grouped to carry out certain communicative tasks like speech presentations, short dramas, discussion panels etc. In this way, learners will be motivated to learn English by using it in a communicative situation. These need to be incorporated into the course syllabus.

Similarly, it is very important to realize that, in second language learning, making mistakes is a part of new language experimentation, and instructors need to let their students know this and also that it is alright to make mistakes. The most important aspect of correction is in how it is done in a way and manner that learners could learn from them.

It is also within the concern of the paper to suggest that, large class situations should be avoided. Groupings should be made not exceeding 100 students. This will allow instructors to know their students and come to see their strengths and weaknesses. Similarly, instructors will also be given the opportunity to spend major portion of class time allowing

students to read, write and speak, using the English medium. This is important because, students learn to read best by reading just like how they learn to speak best by speaking. Thus, communication in English classes should be turned into workshops for students in which the opportunities for learning and individual growth are boundless. And all these opportunities are only possible if larger classes are avoided.

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